

THE ROLE OF TRANSPORTATION FORWARDING COMPANIES IN INTERNATIONAL FREIGHT TRANSPORT AND THE ANALYSIS OF CARGO FLOW

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АННОТАЦИЯ В данной статье рассмотрена роль транспортно-экспедиторских компаний в международных перевозках грузов железнодорожным транспортом и проведен анализ грузов, перевозимых на международных маршрутах в акционерном обществе “УТҮ”.

Ключевые слова: международные перевозки, транспортно-экспедиционные компании, логистический центр, экспедитор, FIATA.

ANNOTATION In this article, an analysis of the role of transportation forwarding companies in international freight transport by railway and the analysis of cargoes transported internationally by "UTY" Joint Stock Company were carried out.

Keywords: international freight forwarding, transportation forwarding company, logistics center, freight forwarder, FIATA.

Introduction

A unified transport complex in the form of cooperative activities of a few strong transport and forwarding companies has emerged in the world. According to information from the International Federation, the global association comprises nearly 8 million employees and includes 35,000 large and medium-sized forwarding companies.

Thus, the main entity providing goods to the carrier remains the forwarder. Forwarders control up to 60% of mainline transport and up to 75% of total international shipping.

The forwarder becomes the logistics system manager, ensuring the planning and forecasting of transportation, the movement of transport vehicles and containers, the delivery time of goods, the storage of cargo and finished products, and the optimization of freight movement. It is anticipated that in the future, 60 to 70 logistics distribution transport hubs will be established, connected by transport corridors linked to regional logistics subsystems. These subsystems will provide access to each shipper and receiver through an unlimited number of forwarders.

The global legislation on transport and forwarding activities (TEF) can be conditionally divided into international and national laws. National legislation aligns to varying degrees with international standards, depending on the level of development of transport forwarding in each country.

The main international agreements and conventions regulating transport and forwarding activities in transport vehicles are as follows:

- The General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT). It regulates general issues of legal regulation of international trade. More than one hundred countries are part of GATT;
- The primary agreement of the World Trade Organization (WTO) concerning the procedures for crossing borders, which establishes unified international requirements for the technical specifications of transport vehicles;
- The Convention on International Multimodal Transport of Goods, established in 1980 among 77 countries. The primary content of this normative act is to establish a legal and regulatory framework that regulates international multimodal transport based on a unified, bilateral transport document. According to the convention, the carrier (forwarder) who declares responsibility for delivering the cargo is considered the “multimodal transport operator”.
- The European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road (ADR), which regulates the requirements for transporting dangerous goods;

- The International Convention on the Customs Treatment of Goods in Transit;
- The Convention on the Contract for the International Carriage of Goods by Road (CMR);
- The International Convention on the Harmonization of Frontier Controls of Goods;
- The Customs Convention on the Temporary Importation of Private Road Vehicles;
- The Customs Convention on Containers, and the Agreement on the International Carriage of Perishable Foodstuffs and on the Special Equipment to be Used for such Carriage (ATP);
- There are several international organizations that develop normative documents with mandatory or advisory status, which are considered when drafting national legislation on transport and forwarding activities and address issues related to the functioning of transport forwarding activities.

The International Federation of Freight Forwarders Associations (FIATA) provides guidelines for regulating transport and forwarding activities (TEF). FIATA has sent a model of transport and forwarding service rules to its members, specifically targeting countries that lack legislation on transport and forwarding services, are in the process of developing it, or require significant revisions. This organization develops the formats for transport and forwarding documents, outlines their formalization, and establishes procedures for implementing TEF.

The Committee on Inland Transport of the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) is undertaking significant work in developing over 50 protocols, conventions, and agreements in the field of transport.

The "Effekt" international information system regulates the technology and format for completing transport and forwarding documents using paperless technology. It also addresses the legal aspects of organizing transportation with various modes of transport.

The legal aspects of organizing transportation with different modes of transport are regulated by the European Conference of Ministers of Transport (ECMT), the International Road Transport Union (IRU), and civil aviation organizations such as ICAO and IATA. These organizations develop recommendations and legal regulations for different modes of transport, including rail transport.

There are several ways to incorporate international agreements and regulatory documents for national forwarders in specific countries. These include:

- Integrating the requirements and rules from the provided documents into national legislation;
- Deciding to implement international standards or regulatory documents within the territory of the given countries;
- Ensuring that the development of national regulatory documents is guided by international regulatory documents;
- Certifying the quality system of a forwarding company or transport-forwarding service in compliance with international requirements (often conducted by neutral bodies located in another country and recognized internationally);
- Implementing tax policies within the framework of TEF to manage the development, methods, and directions of TEF economically;
- Legally protecting all TEF participants, especially citizens (consumers);
- Standardizing TEF from all perspectives, including insurance policies.

The legal basis for the relationship between the client and the forwarder is the transport forwarding contract. The primary principle of this contract is the equality and high level of responsibility of both parties — the client and the forwarder. In practice, the contract can be established through the exchange of documents using various communication methods such as telegraph, teletype, telephone, electronic, etc.

The contract between the client and the forwarder defines their internal jurisdiction, broadly representing the legal relationship between the parties: between

the client and the forwarder, or between the forwarder and a third party on behalf of the client. In this arrangement, the forwarder interacts with the third party not in their own name, but in the name of the client.

We can observe the volume of goods transported internationally by the regional railway hubs of “O‘zbekiston temir yo‘llari” Joint Stock Company from 2021 to 2023 through the following 1-graph.

The clear definition of the mutual rights and responsibilities of TEF participants is reflected in the general rules of transport-forwarding activities and the specific forms of transport-forwarding documents.

1-graph

Global standardization of transport-forwarding activities requires the establishment of a single primary document that reflects the national regulations and considers international legislation. This task is mainly undertaken by FIATA.

Developed countries attach great importance to addressing protectionist barriers concerning national forwarders and shippers. This creates favorable working conditions for domestic companies in the domestic transport-forwarding service

market compared to foreign firms. This is achieved through licensing and tax policies.

In the development of TEF, providing vocational training for employees working in transport-forwarding companies by the state and enhancing their skills through vocational training programs is of great importance. Most types of forwarding activities do not require significant capital or technical infrastructure to implement. Therefore, ensuring the success of a forwarder primarily relies on providing excellent professional training.

Conclusion

To summarize, transportation forwarding companies handle 75% of international freight transport among over 200 countries worldwide. It was found that containerized transport units are the most commonly used in these shipments, constituting over 80% of total transportation. Using the example of “UTY” Joint Stock Company, it was determined that in the international freight transport at the Bukhara regional railway junction, the cargo flow increased by 2%, while it decreased by 1% at the Tashkent regional railway junction.

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